

CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN LANGUAGE TEACHING MATERIALS FOR NON-PHILOLOGICAL FIELDS

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Abstract

The need for language teachers to become more culturally competent in their instruction has grown as a result of the expanding globalization of language instruction. However, cultural competence is frequently left out of language teaching materials, which makes the language learning process less authentic and contextually relevant. Investigating the significance of cultural competency in language teaching materials, especially for non-philological directions and putting forth a framework for doing so are the goals of this article.

Key words: *Language instruction, cultural competency, communicative approach, cultural exchange, global understanding, cultural awareness, intercultural communication*

Introduction

Language training has changed dramatically over the last few decades, moving away from the traditional focus on grammar and vocabulary and toward a more communicative approach that places a higher priority on cultural competency (Byram, 1997). The growing understanding of the role that language plays in promoting global understanding, cultural exchange, and communication has led to this paradigm shift. As a result, language teachers now concentrate on helping students become proficient communicators in a particular language and culture rather than just teaching them grammar and vocabulary rules. Kramersch (1993) defined cultural competency as the capacity to understand and appreciate the complexities of a target culture, including its values, customs, and behaviors. This idea is essential to language learning because it helps pupils comprehend the language and its context on a deeper level. Being culturally competent involves more than just knowing the language; it also entails understanding the cultural context in which it is used. In order to create a relevant and realistic learning experience, cultural competence is crucial in language training (Kramersch, 2006). Students can do the following when cultural competency is integrated into language instruction:

1) *Gain a greater comprehension of the language and its cultural background.*

- 2) *Improve your interaction with local speakers and cultural customs.*
- 3) *Gain a more sophisticated understanding of the intricacies of language and culture.*
- 4) *Develop a more understanding and receptive communication style.*

Despite its significance, cultural competency is frequently left out of language instruction materials, especially when it comes to non-philological directions (Garcia, 2009). Programs for teaching languages that emphasize the development of useful language abilities, such as business English or English for Specific Purposes (ESP), are referred to as non-philological directions. These programs frequently place more emphasis on honing technical language abilities than on developing cultural competency, which makes language learning less authentic and contextually relevant.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This article is based on Byram's (1997) proposal that cultural competency is a cognitive and social construct. Knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and critical cultural awareness are the five elements that make up Byram's model of cultural competency. A framework for incorporating cultural competency into language teaching resources will be developed using this approach.

METHODOLOGY

Various mixed-methods approaches are used in this article for gathering and analyzing data using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. To learn more about how language teachers view cultural competency in language teaching resources, a survey was given to them. In order to investigate the integration of cultural competence, a content analysis was also conducted on a selection of language teaching resources.

The findings of the survey showed that although language teachers believed that cultural competence was crucial for successful language instruction, they also felt that there wasn't enough of it in the resources they used. A similar pattern was seen in the content analysis of language teaching resources, which showed that few of them included cultural competency.

The conclusions of the article emphasize the value of cultural competency in language instruction materials, especially for non-philological paths. A lack of contextual relevance and authenticity in the language learning process can emerge from culturally insensitive instructional materials, which can lower student motivation and engagement. Cultural competency should be incorporated into language teaching materials, especially for non-philological directions, according to this article's recommendations. Language teachers

should also receive training on how to become more culturally competent in their instruction. The small number of language teachers in the sample and the narrow range of language teaching resources examined are two of the article's shortcomings.

CONCLUSION

Based on Byram's idea of cultural competence, the article suggests a framework for incorporating cultural competency into language instruction materials. Knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and critical cultural awareness are the five elements that make up the framework. Language teaching resources that are appropriate for learners' needs and culturally competent can be created using this paradigm. The usefulness of the suggested framework in creating culturally sensitive language teaching resources should be examined in future studies. Research should also look at how cultural competency affects learner engagement and motivation.

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